

A SURVEY ON ASSOCIATION BETWEEN LIFESTYLE RELATED CAUSES OF GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE

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ABSTRACT : The aim of this study is to assess dietary and lifestyle factors associated with GERD (Gastroesophageal reflux disease) through a survey conducted on population of Delhi and Noida, Uttar Pradesh from age group-15 to 45 years and above. GERD is related to many irregular dietary and lifestyle habits (such as a habit of midnight snacking, skipping breakfast, large gap between meals, eating quickly, eating very spicy foods, eating junk food frequently high fatty food and eating beyond fullness). An interval of less than three hours between dinner and bedtime, disturbed sleeping pattern was positively related to GERD, while proper physical exercise was negatively correlated with GERD. Smoking, alcohol consumption and mental state (poor mental state) were positively correlated with GERD. In conclusion, many dietary and lifestyle factors affect the onset of GERD and these factors differ among sex, age groups and job types. Unhealthy lifestyles are closely related to high incidence of suspected GERD. These findings need to be further confirmed in subsequent studies.

Key words : GERD, lifestyle, diet pattern.

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INTRODUCTION

Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) refers to the symptoms and complications caused by the back flow of gastric content into the oesophagus, mouth (including the throat) (Katz *et al*, 2013). The complications of GERD may be the oesophageal mucosa break, ulcer or peptic stricture, Barrett's oesophagus (BE) and even oesophageal carcinoma (Lagergren *et al*, 1999). The common symptoms of GERD include heartburn, regurgitation, nausea, belching and angina-like retrosternal chest pain. However, many patients may present with atypical symptoms, such as abnormal sensation of the pharynx, chest tightness, shortness of breath, cough and asthma, which often led to missed diagnosis and misdiagnosis (Klauser, 1990).

Many studies have focused on the association between GERD and established risk factors, such as age, gender, body mass index (BMI) (Martinucci, 2018), obesity (Lagergren, 2001), tobacco smoking (Ness-Jensen, 2014) and physical activity (Djarv *et al*, 2012).

Typically, GERD begins in the middle age, suggesting that various environmental and lifestyle factors may contribute to its pathophysiology. Dietary factors such as shorter dinner-to-bed time, a high dietary fat intake, obesity and smoking have been implicated in increasing the risk for GERD. Other lifestyle factors include stress, major negative life events, and alcoholism (Fujiwara *et al*, 2008). Similarly, individuals, who consume more coffee, tea and/or citrus fruits and are more prone to GERD (Eslami *et al*, 2017). Recent studies have also shown that smoking is an independent factor in predicting the progression of GERD (Matsuki *et al*, 2013 and Cela *et al*, 2013).

In the present study, we performed the questionnaire-based survey to understand which dietary and lifestyle factors associated with gastroesophageal reflux disease. These aspects included dietary habits, sleeping habits, smoking, physical activity and alcoholism, particular food items and its relation to acidity and other provoked symptoms in gastroesophageal tract. In addition, we analysed that how people deal with those symptoms.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Survey strategy

This survey utilizes google form to collect primary data. Google form is an application in the form of a template or worksheet that can be used independently or together for the purpose of obtaining user information. This application works in Google Drive cloud storage along with other applications such as Google sheets, Google Docs and other enrichments. This template is very easy to understand and use, and is available in many languages.

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdITcZxZQ5WwCRB7dY6VChPq3DiuAx0Fw1B3H6EJzjcg/viewform?vc=0&c=0&w=1&flr=0&usp=mail_form_link

Survey population

Survey is conducted on a population of Delhi and Noida, Uttar Pradesh using criteria such as (i) dietary preferences (ii) alcohol consumption (iii) smoking (iv) sleeping pattern (v) stress management (vi) physical activities.

Data processing methods

Data processing go through several stages, namely: editing (checking and adjusting as needed to the research data, the questionnaire has been filled all or nothing); coding (the process of identifying and classifying research data into numeric scores or character symbols) and scoring (giving a score on each respondent's answer given a score and the scores are arranged).

RESULTS

Survey is conducted in Delhi-Noida region and in total 117 people participated in the survey. The targeted audience were 15 to 45 years and above, out of which majorly responses were from the age group of 20 to 25 years and 25 to 30 years and small population of 15 to 20 years (Fig. 1). A total of 55% of female and 45% of the male members participated in the survey (Fig. 2).

With regard to the lifestyle, it is found in the survey that majority of people have partially active lifestyle and around 12% of the people have sedentary lifestyle (Fig. 3). Out of all the population, around 70% of the people have a lifestyle which involves long sitting hours (Fig. 4).

Survey on sleep pattern shows that, out of the total population, 29.1% of the people do not get sufficient sleep and around 54.7% of people do not have a fixed sleep schedule (Figs. 5 and 6). A total of 37.6% of people usually go to bed after midnight (Fig. 7).

With reference to the smoking habit and alcohol consumption, survey says that around 14.5% of people

Fig. 1 :

Fig. 2 :

Fig. 3 :

Fig. 4 :

among the population are smokers and out of which 45.8% are regular smokers (Figs. 8 and 9). Out of the total population around 28.2% people consume alcohol and 10.5% of them consumes alcohol more than once a week (Figs. 10 and 11).

Survey on eating habits shows that majority of the population prefer a mix of junk and healthy food and around 43.5% of the people have junk food once a week

Fig. 5 :

Fig. 9 :

Fig. 6 :

Fig. 10 :

Fig. 7 :

Fig. 11 :

Fig. 8 :

Fig. 12 :

and a total of 33.7% of the people have junk food twice a week as a part of their regular meal (Figs. 12 and 13). Out of the total population, 65.8% of the people prefer

Fig. 13 :

Fig. 17 :

Fig. 14 :

Fig. 18 :

Fig. 15 :

Fig. 19 :

Fig. 16 :

Fig. 20 :

Fig. 21 :

Fig. 22 :

Fig. 23 :

moderately spicy food and around 6% of people prefer to consume highly spicy food (Fig. 14). A total of 24.8% of the total population consumes caffeine in the morning in the form of tea/coffee (Fig. 15). Out of the total population 37.6% people prefer to have a heavy breakfast (Fig. 16).

With reference to the interval given between two meals, it is noticed in the survey that around 23.9% of the total population, have more than six hours of time interval between two meals of the day (Fig. 17). Out of the total population participated in the survey, it is found that a total of 11.1% of people have more than 14 hours of time interval between the last meal of the day to the first meal of the next day (Fig. 18). Majority of people approximately 58% get indulge into sedentary activity

after consuming dinner and 12.1% to go to sleep immediately (Fig. 19).

It is found in the survey that among all, 43% of the people experience different symptoms related to gastrointestinal problems. 13.7% of the people experience gastric issues, 11.1% of the people experience multiple symptoms and 11.1% of the people experienced burning feeling in the chest/heartburn (Fig. 20). Around 41% of the total population experience symptoms due to consumption of spicy food, high-fat foods, caffeine etc (Fig. 21).

Among the population surveyed, 56.4% of the people are not aware of GERD and around 75% of the population don't prefer to consult a doctor and they prefer home remedies or over-the-counter antacid overcome gastrointestinal issues (Figs. 22 and 23).

DISCUSSION

The survey is conducted in Delhi-Noida region on a total population of 117 people. The targeted audience was between 15 to 45 years of age and above. Out of which major responses came from the participants of age group 20 to 35 years and a small population of 15-20 years.

The sex ratio between the population was found to be 11: 9.

It is concluded from the survey that majority of people have partially active lifestyle and remarkable number of people have sedentary lifestyle. Since majority of people are engaged in office jobs hence, they spend sedentary lifestyle. Out of all the people surveyed, around 70% of the people have a lifestyle which involves long sitting hours. This affects their sleeping pattern also. It is noticed in survey that around 50% of the population do not have a fixed sleeping schedule and they usually go to bed after midnight.

Further, in survey it is seen that large group of population is involved in excessive alcohol consumption, excessive spicy food and fat intake, inadequate intake of vegetables and fruits, excessive intake of cereal and excessive intake of meat, fish, and eggs.

Moreover, lack of awareness regarding relationship between sleep and GERD is also observed in remarkable number of people. Around 50% of population of the people participated in survey were not aware of the GERD and around 75% of the population don't prefer to consult a doctor and they prefer home remedies for over-the-counter ant acid.

CONCLUSION

GERD is a chronic digestive system disease caused by multiple factors and multiple pathways. In the present

survey, it is found that various dietary and lifestyle factors affect the occurrence of GERD. It is noticed in the survey that most of the middle-aged population had disturbed diet and lifestyle pattern. There were also differences in the diet- and lifestyle-related factors related to GERD according to sex and age. Whether the differences in diet and lifestyle structure associated with age and sex are also reasons for the difference in incidence needs further study. Our findings also show majority of the population is not aware of GERD and prefers home remedies or consumption of antacid over consulting a doctor.

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